

AN ANALYSIS OF PARK AND PEOPLE RELATIONSHIP AROUND KAZIRANGA NATIONAL PARK: IMPLICATIONS FOR CONSERVATION AND DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract- Home to the endemic and world famous one horn Rhinoceros and a host to a rich biodiversity, Kaziranga National Park is a World Heritage Site located in the state of Assam, India. The Park also holds a special position as it has a diverse human population from different cultures surrounding the national park. Human interactions with wildlife are a defining experience of human existence. These interactions can be positive or negative. This National Park is unique because of its unique landscape and the dynamics of the park and people relationship. However, the park faces a set of challenges and the large-scale changes fostered by habitat fragmentation, increasing settlements, conflicts with the local community and implications for conservation have been a source of threat. The indigenous people have been facing displacement and are deprived from using the resources from the forests. This in turn leads to resentment amongst the people and become potential cause of grudge in the form of encroachment, poaching, excessive collection of forest products and loss of biodiversity. Also, it is not to be forgotten that the eco-tourism of the region provides remuneration to the local people. In this context, the research aims to analyze the place attachment in fostering community-based management and assess the existing success and failure of the conservation policies taking into account the key challenges and suggesting measures for a sustainable national park. The methodology adopted for the study includes qualitative research in the form of interviews and draws insights from secondary sources of data to meet the objectives.

Key Words: Kaziranga National Park, Place attachment, Community based approach, Challenges, Conservation, Sustainable Park

Introduction

The concern for the symbiotic relationship between human agency and the natural world has been a ubiquitous theme across diverse global cultures. In the spaces of national parks, the human and wildlife interaction is dynamic and complex and is shaped by the lived experiences of the communities residing in the fringes of the parks. These perceptions and attitudes play an important role in fostering conservationist attitudes and help in addressing and solving issues catering to national parks (Petrova, 2011). The community and wildlife need to exist in harmony so that a sustainable park can be developed. The idea of a national park stems back to the west in the 19th

C. A collective consciousness stemmed for the judicious use of natural resources and preservation of natural wilderness (B.Gissibl, 2012). It was under this conservationist movement, the idea of national parks developed and the Yellowstone National Park was established in 1872 in the United States. (Runte, 1977)

The Indian context for national parks, began strikingly in a different ideological paradigm. Wildlife historian Mahesh Rangarajan has reminded us that sport in British India had to be placed in the context of the evolution of the privileged access to game within Britain (Rangarajan, 1996) 'Hunting for sport was not only a form of amusement for the British, but also affirmed their status as racially distinct and close-knit elite' (Conservation Foundation 1972). In the light of the above statement, it can be claimed that the game reserves and sanctuaries were the products of the early twentieth century colonial understanding of Indian fauna and the international fauna preservation movement (Saikia A. , 2009).

The inception of Kaziranga National Park began in this context. In the nineteenth century, the relationship between the wildlife in Assam and colonial state was never cordial, as anywhere in the colonial world. For James Forsyth, a British officer posted in India in 1857 comments, 'The main attraction of India lay in the splendid field it offered for the highest and noblest order of sport, in the pursuit of the wild and savage denizens of its forests and jungles, its mountains and groves' (Rangarajan, India's Wildlife History: An introduction, 2001). Kaziranga was declared a game reserve in the early twentieth century, and was a planter's heaven for the sport of hunting (EP, 1952). The Assamese elites indulged in hunting practices beyond the purpose of recreation but to negotiate culturally with the British. With the passage of time, a number of Assamese took active interest in safeguarding the wildlife and wrote articles on hunting as well as conservation of the

fauna of Kaziranga (Saikia R. , 2003). It was only through the legislative affairs and the space created by the newspaper that the Assamese could carve out a space for expressing opinion for conservation of the wild (Saikia A. , 2009). Over a period of time, the game of hunting took the form of poaching leading to significant killings of the animals in the area. Along with this, conflicts surfaced between the game reserve and the agrarian practices. The unique topography of Kaziranga and the nature of its ecology posed a serious threat to the conservation programme of the mid- twentieth century. The agrarian frontiers were expanding at the cost of the space for the wildlife thus leading to conflicts between the villagers and the wildlife.

Following this Kaziranga embarked on a journey of becoming a National Park. Since the establishment of the Kaziranga Wildlife Sanctuary, it essentially remained a place for game and recreation for a limited few. In the post-independent period, the attitude towards the wildlife sanctuaries had changed. With the cooperation of the professional wildlife conservationists it was now realized that the protection of wildlife inside the sanctuaries needed the cooperation of the neighbouring people. The problems arising from close contact between the human habitation and wildlife could not be evaded anymore and hence the program of national parks was emphasized. Henceforth, Kaziranga was declared a National Park in the year 1905 and subsequently a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 1985.

The Park is a unique landscape, archetype of biodiversity and ecosystem services. In today's scenario a number of villages are located at the fringe of the national park and the dynamics of the interaction between the park and the people is very interesting. Human interactions with wildlife are a defining experience of human existence (Mekonen, 2020). Contestations occur between humans and wildlife when the needs and behaviour of wildlife negatively impact humans or vice versa (Sillero-Zubiri, 2001). It is stated that since human wildlife conflict is a reciprocal process, both of them are negatively affected by the conflict, and is one of the most complex issues facing wildlife conservation (Frank B., 2019).

Scholars are in quest of ways to refocus policy-relevant conflict research on finding pathways toward human-wildlife coexistence and coadaptation (Carter, 2016). To foster this coexistence and coadaptation, the way in which the local community around the park make 'sense of the place' becomes very vital to promote community-based conservation. Escobar (2001) questions: how do people encounter places, perceive them and endow them with significance? According to Harvey (2001) place is engrossed in the way people experience and make meanings; people and their environments, and how places and identities are mutually constructed and constituted. In the context of the landscape dynamics of the park and the people, the place attachment, place dependency and place identity become key subsets of this sense of place. Theoretical and methodological considerations of place include how place meanings develop over time and how people become attached to places (Agnew 1987; Tuan 1977 and 1991; Massey 1994; Bender 2001; Ingold 2000). These subsets of sense of place imbibe certain attitudes amongst the community which is either conditioned in a positive or negative manner depending on various factors which determine the community centered approach of conserving the park and foster a symbiotic relationship.

Scholarship on Kaziranga National Park has mostly been restricted to drawing on the history of the park, the Land use and Land Cover Change, the social composition of the peripheral villages, conservation measures and challenges faced by the park. There is a lack of research on the aspect that how in the National Park space, place profounds a centre of human existence to which people have deep emotional ties and is a part of the complex mechanisms and processes through which these local communities define themselves and build cordial ties with the landscape and wildlife of the National Park. In this context, the paper tries to unpack and understand this aspect and see how this notion of 'sense of place' built positively or negatively helps in promoting or reducing community-based conservation and in navigating a path towards a sustainable park.

Study Area

Kaziranga National Park, a UNESCO World Heritage site, is encompassed in the districts of Golaghat, Nagaon and Sonitpur covering an area of 430km² of Assam. The park is divided into five ranges: Eastern range at Agratoli, Central Range at Kohora, Western Range at Bagori, Burapahar Range at Ghorakati and the Northern Range at Biswanath. Endemic to the one-horned rhinoceros the park is characterized with a diverse species of flora and fauna. The fringe villages inhabited by the local communities are ethnically diverse and share a unique relationship with the park.

The research is carried out in the fringe villages of Kohora, Bagori and Burapahar from the wildlife ranges of the park. The selection of these villages has been done as these are the major entry points to the park and are easily accessible. These villages are dominated by the Assamese, tribals and Nepali people.

Methodology

A mixed methodology has been adopted to have a better understanding of the study area. A sample size of 75 households have been studied together from the three villages of Kohora, Bagori and Burapahar. Qualitative methodology has been used in the form of semi-structures interviews and household survey. Quantitative data has been drawn from secondary sources like government reports, archives, web sources, journals etc. Snowball sampling has been used as the respondents were reluctant to participate in the study without proper reference.

The research is based on the many conversations, mostly interviews that were conducted in the villages and also with the forest officials. Narrative analysis has been done as interpretations are shaped by particular circumstances that exist as the study unfolds. The realities are illuminated through the process of detailed descriptions of the experiences of the people (Appleton and King,2002)

Inside Story of Kaziranga National Park: Challenges and Issues

The landscape of Kaziranga National Park has undergone a rapid transformation over a period of years. The park is surrounded by people on all sides. Bustling townships of Bokakhat and Jakhlabandha are notable in the area. The park is spread across the districts of Golaghat, Nagaon and Sonitpur. (Report by Govt. of Assam, 2014). The park covers an area of 430km² currently, though there are proposals to add on an additional 454.50km² by including the Brahmaputra Riverto the north and south of the Mikir hills.

The park boasts the most extensive remaining grassland in the area, spanning approximately 50 kilometers along the southern edge of the Brahmaputra. The yearly river floods serve to renew the wetlands and foster the thriving growth of the grassland areas (Choudhury, 2004). Satellite data indicates how there has been severe erosion caused by the Brahmaputra and floods which have caused numerous animal deaths timely in the park (Vasu, 2003).

Kaziranga National Park, now globally recognized as a protected area, grapples with ongoing issues, notably persistent poaching threats. However, its primary future challenges arise externally, driven by regional factors such as Assam government's development priorities and broader issues like population growth and increased economic expectations. This mirrors challenges faced globally, where effective management within protected areas is jeopardized by shifts in the surrounding landscape (Mathur V.B, 2003). Some key landscape scale issues have been discussed in brief in this paper.

- i. *The NH 37 and Habitat Fragmentation:* The NH 37 which runs to the south of the Kaziranga National Park has recently been a hotbed of construction activity with hotels, resorts, shops and commercial space for both locals and visitors. The quantity of traffic on the highway has increased dramatically. The corridors for animal

movement have been blocked due to this and has led to the confinement of the giant mammals in the park for a longer period of time resulting in habitat damage (Bonal, 2004) thus creating a barrier effect. The NH 37 has also bifurcated the park into two parts. During floods the animals while trying to move to the uplands at Karbi Anglong from the other side of the park get killed in car accidents. This habitat fragmentation has a serious concern to be addressed.

- ii. *Land erosion*: In the last century, Kaziranga celebrated conservation successes with rising populations of endangered species. However, these achievements pose new management challenges for the relatively small park, compounded by ongoing land loss to floods in its unique ecosystem. In the mid-1980s, the Assam Government proposed additions to Kaziranga National Park to establish wildlife corridors, escape routes during floods, and compensate for park area loss to erosion by including Brahmaputra chapories. Six planned additions were notified, with three awaiting approval for legal, administrative, and financial reasons. These extensions aim to offer additional habitat for the exponentially growing wildlife population, as indicated by recent census data (Govt of Assam Report, 2019). This has been an increased site of contestation as a large number of people will be displaced from the park.
- iii. *Conflict between humans and wildlife*: Human-wildlife conflict arises from direct community losses and is further complicated by people's attitudes toward nature, influenced by factors such as religious affiliations, ethnicity, emotional ties to the area, and cultural beliefs. In Kaziranga, the animals frequently cross the park boundaries destroying crops and property, threatening human life and at times even causing human deaths. The resentment and animosity towards wildlife is expressed through various encounters and apparently the cost of conservation is largely borne by the communities residing on the fringe of the park (Brandon et al., 1998; Terborgh et al., 2002).

The Park and the People: Two sides of the same coin

- **Narratives of the local community**

Human-wildlife conflict is a probable consequence of agricultural activities, stemming from the historical occurrence of damage inflicted by wild animals on crops. This conflict has likely persisted since the inception of agriculture by humans (Madden, 2004). According to the World Parks Congress Recommendation, conflicts between human and wildlife occur when each one adversely affects each other.

The relationship that is shared between the community and the park is dynamic. In order to understand the complexities and dynamics of this relationship to address the issues and develop solutions to it to make it a sustainable park it becomes essential to understand the perspectives and experiences of the people living in proximity to the park. Ever since its inception there have been conflicts in Kaziranga. When tensions rise between local communities and wildlife, and management fails to resolve the issues, the conflict expands beyond just human-wildlife interactions to become a conflict 'among humans regarding wildlife.' (Medhi, 2020).

The occupational profile of the villagers in KNP mostly is limited to agriculture, whereas some of them are engaged in the dhabas sprouting near the highways, a few as construction workers and some as labourers in adjacent tea gardens. While narrating the experience of living near Kaziranga, a resident of the Kohora village said, '*Kaziranga is our pride, since my childhood I have resided here, it is my source of income and my family runs from this. I am a jeep driver at the safari*'. This reflects the person's positive attachment to the place since he has grown up in that particular environment. Also, as Vorkinn and Rise (2001) highlight that the development of socio-economic and cultural linkages to an area result in a higher degree of sensitivity towards the park and has a profound impact on them for indulging in conservation practices.

Multiple narratives were encountered as the different households were traversed. Sarita Devi a woman belonging from the tribal community shares her experience '*Kaziranga is our source of livelihood, selling products derived from the forest we used to get money. Earlier when we used to visit the forest if we something suspicious we use to inform the guards but recently we have been restricted from accessing anything from the forest. How do we survive?*'. Unaware of notifications concerning the reservation of forest areas, the people continued their daily activities in the forest, resulting in them being categorized as encroachers in their own dwellings (Nongbri, 1999). This has in turn led to the people develop negative attitudes and hence they refrain from engaging in the conservation and management of the wildlife as they feel that since their interests are not

Often, the cost of conservation is borne by the communities. Even when their crops and property are destroyed by elephants, with the highest degree of protection and safeguarding offered by the Wildlife Protection Act 1972 to Kaziranga, the people have very less or no control in such situations. The restrictions prohibit the people from protecting their crops and livestock by traditional methods and practices like culling (Watve, 2016).

A villager residing in Bagori confided that '*We live in a state of constant fear apprehensive of being rendered homeless by herds of elephants, a situation which we had to encounter a few years back*'. Though there is an acceptance amongst the community that they are located at a disadvantaged location, they have grievances against the

authorities as well. People have shared that they understand that the forest department does not instigate the animals to attack or kill their cattle. It is their destiny since they stay there. If they would have got compensation against the damage caused, they would have positive affiliations about the authorities.

Another recent issue grappling Kaziranga is the eviction of people and their displacement for implementation of the six additions to the park. The neighbouring communities often tend to disapprove conservation measures due to fear of eviction and restriction from resource collection. This in turn leads to them develop negative perceptions about the place and they often express their grudge by harming the animals, helping poachers and pay interest in adopting a community approach to make the park sustainable (Sims, 2010). It was observed that a feeling of imposition was dominant in the narratives of the local communities.

Some respondents of the Kohora and Burapahar villages have expressed their stances that due to the national park, the tourism industry is booming in the region and it provides them employment opportunities and has also led to increase in their incomes. As Svalbard claims how people's reactions to environmental impacts vary according to the place meanings and their affiliations. A respondent opined that the declaration of the park as a tiger reserve ignoring the local sentiments worsened park management-local community relationship. Such conflicts are rooted in historical wounds, cultural misunderstandings, socioeconomic needs as well as gaps in trust and communication over how wildlife can be conserved ensuring the well-being of the people at the same time (Madden, 2004).

Narratives of the Forest Officials

It has been argued that the human-wildlife conflict within national parks could be an expression of human-human conflict rather than the reverse. The human-human conflict in this context may involve disputes between the park management authority and local communities or conflicts among communities living near the park (Dickman, 2010). Some local communities exhibit increased dissatisfaction with wildlife when they perceive the park as an imposition by an external entity, specifically the state, and consider the wildlife to be the state's possession (Naughton-Treves, 2005). While recording the experiences of a forest guard, he recalled that the staff under the park are referred to as *chaprasis* (clerks) by the local people. A forest officer narrated that when they ask the local people to inform them of animal sighting in the human-dwelling areas, they respond by saying that '*why should we do your job? or 'if you are not on time to handle the situation, we will cause harm to your animals'*' It brings into light that the national parks infuse a sense of alienation amongst the communities from the wildlife with whom they had coexisted.

Another officer expressed his shock at the aggression displayed by the local community while chasing away stray wildlife. He mentioned that employing such frightening strategies distressed the animals, leading them to cause more harm to people and property. This display of violence could suggest an underlying resentment among the community or an opportunity for retaliation against the wildlife. Despite this the people in the fringes of the park show a lot more tolerance in comparison to people located at other national parks like Sariska Tiger Reserve².

There have been instances as well where the forest guards have had encounters with the local people and shot them in the misconception of a poacher whereas they might just have been navigating the area for grazing their livestock. Such incidents lead to negative interpretations of the experiences and people react in a hostile manner in the conservation and management strategies.

Conclusion

An analysis of the park and people relationship through the paper shows the experiences which are shaped positively and negatively in the geographical setting of the park. Some measures can be taken into account to foster community-based approach of the wildlife management and conservation and ensure the sustainability of the park. A policy to utilize the local communities from the fringe villages as casual workers, field informants and camp boys can be enforced to bridge the gap between the authorities and the people. Working in close association will build trust between them.

Young population of the village can be appointed as tourist guides. During the crucial time of floods, volunteers can play a key role by guarding the highway so that the animals are not killed or injured. The compensation policy of the government needs to be boosted for a speedy process so that the community can develop allegiance and positive affiliation towards the park. A consistent effort to provide the local communities with alternative modes of livelihood can help in ensuring local community cooperation of the wildlife. The people engaged in such conservation approach should be paid properly as it would act as a positive reinforcement for the people to be more closely associated with the park and at the same time promote more participation in the stewardship process. Indigenous participation has always been the key behind the development of a sustainable park as they are the ones who have the best knowledge of their own place.

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